

Hybrid FSO/RF Transmission over Shared Antenna Aperture:

Hybrid Optical / RF Feeder for 6G Radio Access with Shared FSO / FR3 Aperture and $\Sigma\Delta$ -Modulation Switching

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Abstract:

We present a simplified air interface for facilitating a wireless RF/FSO relay in an optically fed amplify & forward radio access architecture. We accomplish EVMs of 5.9% and 9.4% for an optical fronthaul budget of 19 dB when switching between FSO and FR3-band modes.

1. Introduction

The continuous increase in aggregated access capacity makes free-space optical (FSO) communication a critical element in 6G feeder links [1]. However, propagation over an FSO channel is strongly impacted by atmospheric conditions. While turbulence can be mitigated through beamforming [2, 3] or large-core optics [4], the strong attenuation of 50⁺ dB/km due to dense fog [5] or beam blocking due to snow can prevent communication – even over short reach if the power margins are not sufficiently large. Although mid-infrared optics can be a possible solution to this and a first bandwidth scaling has been demonstrated for transmitters [6], the immaturity of component technologies at longer wavelengths renders the hybrid transmission of FSO/RF signals as a more compelling approach to mitigate channel outage [7]. Earlier works have proven the robustness of sub-THz or mm-wave frequencies [8-12]. Moreover, the same physical channel can be used for paired transmission by blending the optical and RF channel through insertion of dichroic filters at both link ends [13]. However, RF channels do not necessarily provide the required data capacity equivalent to their FSO counterpart, especially in case of lower FR3- / FR2-band carrier frequencies.

In this work, we demonstrate a simplified air interface with a shared aperture for its joint FSO/RF antenna feeder, together with simple switching between intensity- or phase-modulated sigma-delta ($\Sigma\Delta$) modulation to change between digitized and analogue radio transmission modes over FSO or FR3-band RF channel, respectively. We leverage on simplified fronthaul transceivers that integrate a photonic up-conversion function and demonstrate both, hybrid FSO/RF and relayed RF transmission in a bent-pipe scenario, involving a fronthauled radio head and a relay node as feeder for local RF-based access.

2. Wireless Relay with Shared Air Aperture

Hybrid FSO/RF transmission over an air interface with shared aperture (Fig. 1a) can provide resiliency to unfavorable weather. In the adopted scheme, the OFDM radio signal is transmitted at its intermediate frequency f_{OFDM} as a $\Sigma\Delta$ -coded binary signal [14]. This digitized radio-over-fiber transmission allows the use of simple optical 2-level transmitters [15]. Non-return to zero (NRZ) intensity modulation (IM) can then be used to encode this $\Sigma\Delta$ signal for FSO transmission with subsequent direct photodetection. On the other hand, the alternative RF-based over-the-air (OTA) transmission mode will build on photonic up-conversion, for which a local oscillator (LO), is optically synchronized with a spectral harmonic of the $\Sigma\Delta$ signal. For this purpose, the digitized radio is encoded in return to zero (RZ) format, which together with the $\Sigma\Delta$ oversampling yields a harmonic that is spaced by ν_{RZ} from the optical carrier Λ . For the example shown in Fig. 1a, an FR3-band carrier frequency of $\nu_{\text{FR3}} = 16.5$ GHz is obtained by choosing $\nu_{\text{RZ}} = 15.5$ GHz and $f_{\text{OFDM}} = 1$ GHz. Moreover, phase modulation (PM) can further improve the sensitivity when involving coherent reception in combination with photonic up-conversion. The switch between FSO- and RF-based OTA modes can then be simply made by choosing bias, drive and line code for the optical modulation at the central office (CO).

(TET).

At the RRH, the signal is split to feed the FSO mode and the photonic up-converter of the RF mode for the first relay link. For the **FSO mode**, the $\Sigma\Delta$ signal at the fronthaul is transparently relayed to the REL node over the WR-51 based air interface, which is augmented by a 3" lens ($f = 85$ mm) to provide the shared aperture. The FSO link is terminated by a simple PIN/TIA receiver with RF limiter. The IF radio signal is up-converted to the FR3 carrier frequency of 16.5 GHz with a local RF-LO (f_{u3}). RF management is further simplified by supplying this RF-LO on a second fronthaul wavelength λ_{up3} , in parallel to the $\Sigma\Delta$ radio signal (see inset in Fig. 2a). The radio signal is then distributed from the REL node to the TET, using open-boundary double-ridged horn antennas with a gain of 15 dBi. There, the received radio is down-converted through a RF-LO to an IF of 2 GHz and the error vector magnitude (EVM) is assessed after digitization of the OFDM signal through a real-time scope.

For the **RF mode**, the RRH photonically up-converts the $\Sigma\Delta$ radio through a transistor-outline packaged electroabsorption-modulated laser (EML) with integrated micro-Peltier. We build on its function as coherent homodyne receiver, as proven earlier [16]. In the present work, the EML emission Γ is injection-locked to the RZ harmonic ν_{RZ} so that the OFDM signal at $f_{OFDM} = -1$ GHz from $\Lambda = 1546.45$ nm is up-converted to 16.5 GHz in the FR3-band. Manual polarization control (MPC) is applied at the CO to account for single-polarization coherent detection. However, polarization-independent operation of a coherent EML receiver has been shown elsewhere [17]. After signal conditioning by a 50 Ω low-noise amplifier (LNA) at the EAM photodiode, the up-converted signal is bandpass-filtered (BPF) and boosted before its RF relay over OTA-R. The FR3-band radio can be simply reamplified at REL and further distributed over OTA-D to the TET.

4. Photonic Up-Conversion from $\Sigma\Delta$ to FR3 Band

Figure 2b presents the optical spectra of the transmitted signals that are modulated on the optical carrier Λ , together with the EML emission Γ . The EML locks on the RZ harmonic ν_{RZ} to facilitate photonic up-conversion of the OFDM radio signal adjacent to Λ to the FR3 band frequency $\nu_{FR3} = 16.5$ GHz. The optical carrier suppression through optical PM is 33.7 dB, while the RZ-induced locking harmonic ν_{RZ} is enhanced by 19.6 dB when compared to NRZ coding.

The signal spectrum received by the EML in the RF mode is reported in Fig. 1c. The sensitivity gain due to optical PM can be clearly seen in the spectra. Moreover, the suppression of Λ relaxes the filtering requirements (T_{BPF} in Fig. 3a) before OTA transmission of the FR3 radio at $\nu_{FR3} = 16.5$ GHz. The unlocked EML receiver causes a small offset of the NRZ-PM signal from ν_{FR3} , as can be noticed from the close-up in Fig. 3a. The down-converted radio after OTA-D transmission at its IF of 2 GHz is shown in Fig. 3b. There is no fading noticed in the envelope of the OFDM spectrum.

5. FR3-Band Radio Transmission Performance

The EVM performance for the **FSO mode** over the relay link OTA-R is discussed in Fig. 3c as function of the optical budget (OB) at the fronthaul link. The back-to-back performance till the RRH yields a baseline EVM of 2.4% at an OB of 19 dB (\circ). This low EVM is a result of the noise-robust digitized $\Sigma\Delta$ transmission over the fronthaul. After fiber-based back-to-back relay over OTA-R and up-conversion of the IF radio signal to 16.5 GHz at node REL through a local synthesizer and subsequent RF transmission over the access link OTA-D, the EVM degrades by 3.5% at the same OB (\bullet) since considerable noise is incurred for the now analogue radio transmission. There is no EVM penalty at this OB when (i) instead providing a remote FR3-band RF carrier through a second wavelength over the fronthaul and relay link (\blacktriangle) and (ii) after populating the fronthaul link with transmission fiber (\square). A dynamic range of 13.6 dB can be supported. This range reduces to 7 dB when feeding OTA-R over FSO with the shared antenna aperture (\blacksquare). Despite this impact due to FSO coupling loss, the accomplished EVM remains similarly at 5.9% for an OB of 19 dB.

Fig. 3: (a) Up-converted FR3 radio at RRH and (b) received radio at TET. EVM performance over (c) FSO-, (d) RF relay modes.

Figure 3d presents the radio transmission performance when switching to the **RF mode** at the relay OTA-R. A back-to-back RZ-PM fronthaul feed of the $\Sigma\Delta$ signal and evaluation of the signal before OTA-R transmission indicates a margin of up to 4.3% towards the 16-QAM EVM limit of 12.5% (\circ). Moreover, a dynamic range of 12.9 dB is supported. This power range is limited by the emergence of non-linear terms at lower OB values and the loss of EML locking at the upper OB boundary. There is no notable penalty when adding the transmission fiber (\bullet). For additional OTA-R transmission of the radio signal over the shared-aperture antenna configuration (\blacksquare), we see a reduction in the dynamic range by 1.2 dB towards higher ROP levels. This is attributed to saturation effects arising from the power amplifier at the antenna link. However, the minimum EVM of 8.5% for OTA-R transmission remains similar, as it is evidenced by the EVM per OFDM sub-carrier that is included in Fig. 3b (\blacklozenge). There is no significant difference in EVM between the lensed (\blacksquare) and lens-less (\square) OTA-R link. For the sake of completeness, Fig. 3c includes the EVM for optical RZ-IM signal transmission (\blacktriangle). As expected, this intensity format is penalized by 4.7 dB in terms of reception sensitivity, while the dynamic range is retained due to a later onset of saturation at higher ROP. On the contrary, an exceedingly high EVM applies to NRZ coding. This is because the EML is not able to optically synchronize the photonic up-conversion process since it remains free-running in absence of a locking harmonic, such as provided through ν_{RZ} in case of RZ coding (Fig. 2b). Transmission over both RF links, OTA-R and OTA-D, leads to a small additional EVM penalty of 0.4 to 0.8 dB (\blacklozenge).

6. Conclusions

We have experimentally demonstrated the physical integration of a FSO transmission mode in a point-to-point FR3-band RF link. Through use of a $\Sigma\Delta$ representation for the radio signal and simple coding/modulation switching, the point-to-point FSO fronthaul towards a signal-distributing RF node can be substituted by FR3-band relay that is assisted by photonic up-conversion to retain centralized RF management. The EVMs of 5.9% and 9.4% at an OB of 19 dB for the two transmission modes, which are $\geq 3\%$ below the 16-QAM EVM limit, prove this point. A reduction of the EVM in the RF mode is expected for a photonic up-converter that replaces its LNA stage with a noise-optimized EML+TIA photoreceiver.

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